

[white paper]

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[awaiting peer review]

Void numbers

Open Mathematics Collaboration*[†]

March 18, 2023

Abstract

We present nonzero numbers whose square vanishes for pedagogical purposes.

keywords: void number, dual number, number theory

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/ur7me/download>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7747086>

Note

1. *The author acknowledges having reinvented the wheel and recognizes this as an example of a false positive.*
2. Dual numbers were introduced in 1873 by William Clifford [1].
3. This white paper still serves as a didactic resource.
4. ***Open science strives to publish not only positive results, but also false positives and negative results.***

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Introduction

5. The creation and discovery of new numbers is inspirational [2, 3].
6. We present the *void numbers*, following the same line of thought as the imaginary number i , but applied to *zero*.
7. The word *void* refers to the term **quadractic void**.

Void numbers

8. Let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$.
9. We define the set of **void numbers** as

$$\mathcal{V} = \{a + bv \mid v^2 = 0, v \neq 0\}.$$

Final Remarks

10. Isomorphisms?

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [4, 5].

*Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Send your contribution to mplobo@uft.edu.br.

Supplementary files

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [6, 7].

How to cite this paper?

<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ur7me>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7747086>

Acknowledgements

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Agreement

The author agrees with [5].

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References

[1] Wikipedia. Dual number.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dual_number

[2] Conway, John H. On numbers and games. CRC Press, 2000.

- [3] Knuth, Donald E. *Surreal numbers*. Addison-Wesley, 2017.
- [4] Lobo, Matheus P. “Microarticles.” *OSF Preprints*, 28 Oct. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ejrct>
- [5] Lobo, Matheus P. “Simple Guidelines for Authors: Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics.” *OSF Preprints*, 15 Nov. 2019.
<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/fk836>
- [6] Lobo, Matheus P. “Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics (OJMP).” *OSF*, 21 Apr. 2020. <https://osf.io/6hzyp/files>
- [7] <https://zenodo.org/record/7747086>
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